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Report on magnetic shielding for high quality superconducting resonators

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ABSTRACT

This paper reports on the development of a passive and active magnetic shielding concept for a cryomodule housing four superconducting 704 MHz RF cavities. A test stand for magnetic measurements was then established along with a measurement procedure and used to quantify the magnetisation and shielding of the empty cryomodule. In addition to the original scope, a measurement device was developed and tested to quantify on small samples the magnetic flux, which remains trapped in superconductors after entering the Meissner state. These measurements can be used to better quantify the requirements for magnetic shielding of cryomodules and they allow for systematic studies of material treatments in order to increase flux expulsion, which in turn can reduce the need for magnetic shielding or increase the quality factor of cavities for a certain magnetic shielding configuration.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

This document summarizes the work done within the frame of Deliverable D4.1 at CERN. The general theme is to minimise the effect of ambient magnetic fields on the residual surface resistance of superconducting bulk Niobium cavities and thus to reduce the electrical power consumption.

The 1st part gives a theoretical introduction, the 2nd part develops and describes the design of a passive and active magnetic shielding for a cryomodule. Part 3 reports on the measurement of the magnetic shielding of the empty cryo-vessel and its magnetisation as delivered from manufacturing. Part 4 covers the development and test of a simple device for the fast and reproducible measurement of the flux expulsion efficiency of superconducting material samples.

1. Introduction

This deliverable aims at improving existing technology for superconducting cavities. Within the frame of WP4 “Efficient Energy Management” the goal is to increase efficiency of superconducting cavities by lowering their surface resistance, which decreases the power needs for the cryogenic system.

The classical description of the surface resistance of superconductors is based on the Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer Theory [1], which defines a temperature (T) and frequency (ω) dependent resistance, the so-called BCS resistance, and a residual resistance R_{res} that accounts for all other contributions to the surface resistance:

$$R_S = R_{BCS}(T) + R_{res} = \left(\frac{A\omega^2}{T} \right) e^{-\frac{\Delta}{kT}} + R_{res}$$

This work focuses on the contribution of ambient magnetic fields (e.g. earth’s magnetic field) to the residual resistance. In an ideal superconductor all magnetic field lines are expelled by the Meissner effect [2] once the material is cooled to temperatures below the critical temperature (T_c). Type-II superconductors [3] such as Niobium (Nb), show an incomplete Meissner effect in which some of the flux lines remain trapped to pinning centres in the material. The part of the residual surface resistance $R_{res} = R_{fl} + R_r$ attributed to flux trapping can be written as:

$$R_{fl} = B_0 \cdot \eta(l, \nabla T, \dots) \cdot S(l, \omega, B_{RF})$$

With B_0 being the ambient magnetic field, η the flux trapping efficiency, and S the sensitivity to trapped flux. In order to reduce R_{fl} one can: a) apply magnetic shielding to reduce B_0 , which is the main topic of this work; b) reduce the flux trapping efficiency, for instance by using a large temperature gradient when crossing the critical temperature; or c) reduce the sensitivity. Today we know from cavity tests that the manufacturing and heat treatment history have an influence on b) and c) but we are unable to make precise predictions and reliable test methods for material samples are lacking.

In Section 2 we develop a shielding concept for a cryomodule, which is foreseen to house a string of four 704 MHz 5-cell cavities. In section 3 we present measurements that were done on the magnetic shielding effect of an empty cryo-vessel and in Section 4, we look in more detail at the flux expulsion efficiency and describe a device that was developed to measure exactly this quantity on material samples.

2. Development of passive and active magnetic shielding for a 4-cavity cryomodule.

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The 4-cavity cryomodule was designed in the frame of a study for a superconducting proton linac at CERN [4]. It was conceived for four 5-cell bulk niobium superconducting cavities resonating at 704.4 MHz. In order to reach the nominal quality factor of $Q = 10^{10}$ and an accelerating gradient of 25 MV/m, the average surface resistance R_s has to be below 27 n Ω . This can be translated into a specification for the maximum tolerable ambient magnetic field of $B_{amb} < 5 \mu\text{T}$ on the cavity surface. However, in order to enable full Q recovery after a magnetic quench without warming up (above T_c) and cooling down the cavity, a field level of $< 0.1 \mu\text{T}$ at the cavity surface is desirable [5]. With an ambient magnetic field in the order of 50 μT the goal is to reach a shielding factor of $S = 500$ for fields which are orthogonal (S_{\perp}) or parallel (S_{\parallel}) to the surface of the cryomodule. More details can be found in [6].

2.2 DESIGN OF PASSIVE MAGNETIC SHIELDS

The proposed design consists of 2 layers of magnetic shielding: i) cold magnetic shields around helium vessels of the cavities, and ii) a warm magnetic shield on the inside of the cryo-vessel as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Cold and warm magnetic shielding for the 4-cavity cryomodule.

The cold cryophy[®] shield ($\mu_r, \text{cryophy} = 15,000$) has a thickness of 1 mm dictated by mechanical integration constraints. For the warm mu-metal shield ($\mu_r, \text{mumetal} = 50,000$) a thickness of 3 mm was chosen. For a simple analytic estimate both layers are assumed to be perfect cylinders, which are magnetically decoupled. For this idealised case one finds a theoretical shielding factor for parallel magnetic fields of $S_{\parallel} = 840$. In order to take into account the many penetrations of the shields for couplers, tuners, feedthroughs, etc, a numerical simulation was performed with CST EM Studio[®]. The effect of these various openings can be appreciated in Fig. 2, which shows the combined shielding effect of the warm and cold shields for orthogonal and parallel magnetic fields.

Figure 2: Absolute magnetic field values when combining cold and warm magnetic shields.

While the orthogonal field B_{\perp} is well shielded there is significant penetration of the parallel field B_{\parallel} . One can see that due to the large openings of the cold shield around the end groups, the end cells are exposed to magnetic field levels up to $5 \mu\text{T}$. This means that the passive shielding provides adequate conditions to reach a quality factor of $Q = 10^{10}$, but it is not sufficient to enable fast quench recovery without a thermal cycle.

2.3 ACTIVE MAGNETIC COMPENSATION

The magnetic field level of at the cavity surface can be further reduced by applying active magnetic compensation with coils on the outside of the cryo-vessel. By locating these coils around the position of the cavity tuners – located on the right-hand side of each cavity in Fig. 3 – and by fine-tuning the electric current in the coils, the fields that penetrate towards the cavities via the tuner-side can be reduced significantly. Figure 3 shows that this method reduces the maximum ambient field level at any cavity surface to $< 0.2 \mu\text{T}$. Together with the shielding factor of the empty cryomodule (see next chapter) it is thus possible to reach sub- μT field levels.

Figure 3: The effect of cold and warm magnetic shields plus compensating coils for ambient magnetic field parallel to the vessel.

3. Magnetic shielding measurements for the high-gradient four-cavity cryomodule.

3.1 INTRODUCTION

In order to assess the shielding effect and possible magnetisation of the empty cryomodule, a magnetic measurement was performed on the module. This chapter describes the measurement method, the instruments and summarises the results.

Figure 4: Measurement paths along the beam axis (z) and in x direction.

3.2 MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT AND PRINCIPLE

The measurements were performed with a Bartington flux-gate magnetometer on discrete locations along the beam axis in z -direction and on transverse lines of sight through the openings of the module in x -direction (see Fig. 4). Simple wooden sticks were used to position the magnetometer. A first measurement without the module was taken and a good agreement was found between the measurement and the predictions of the World Magnetic Model. In order to exclude effects of vectorial superposition of a potential magnetisation of the vessel with the ambient field, the measurements were made in 2 orthogonal orientations of the module.

3.3 MEASUREMENTS INSIDE THE MODULE

The absolute value of the magnetic field on axis inside of the module is shown in Fig. 5 and the measurements along the perpendicular axes is shown in Fig. 6. One can see that the vessel provides a shielding factor between 2 and 3. Furthermore it was found that the vessel is slightly magnetized to a level of $\sim 1/3$ ($13 \mu\text{T}$) of the ambient magnetic field. Higher magnetic fields of up to $80 \mu\text{T}$ were found locally in the vicinity of the main welds of the vessel. With the foreseen warm and cold magnetic shields this value will still be reduced to the μT level at the location of the cavities and will thus not perturb the operation of the cavities. Hence there is no need for a demagnetisation of the vessel. The full set of measurements can be found in [6].

Figure 5: Absolute magnetic field along the axis.

Figure 6: Absolute magnetic field along different perpendicular axes.

3. Efficiency of magnetic flux expulsion

3.1 INTRODUCTION & MOTIVATION

In order to better quantify and hopefully to reduce the requirements for magnetic shielding in cryomodules, a measurement device called “flux lens” was developed and tested. It allows to quantify the magnetic flux, which remains trapped in superconductors after entering the Meissner state. With this device systematic studies on optimum conditions for flux expulsion can be conducted, with the goal to maximise the quality factor of superconducting cavities and potentially even to reduce the need for magnetic shielding.

Within the frame of this task an ARIES workshop on flux trapping was held at CERN, 8-9 November 2018 [8], looking specifically at the 3 components of the residual surface resistance, which influence the trapping of magnetic flux in superconducting cavities: i) magnetic shielding, ii) flux expulsion efficiency, and iii) sensitivity to magnetic flux. As mentioned above, flux expulsion is a function of the material’s cold-working and heat treatment history. Figure 7 shows a measurement presented at the Workshop, of flux expulsion versus temperature gradient of 1.3 GHz nitrogen doped cavities built for the upgrade of the US Linac Coherent Light Source at Stanford (LCLS-II), from different Niobium lots [9]. As nitrogen doped cavities show a high sensitivity to flux trapping, a high flux expulsion efficiency is mandatory to reach the LCLS-II performance goals of $Q = 2.5 \times 10^{10}$ at 16 MV/m. As shown in Fig. 7, the target number for flux expulsion was not achieved with cavities made from certain material lots.

Figure 7: Flux expulsion vs temperature gradient for LCLS-II cavities made with Nb from different origins. Courtesy: A. Palzcewski, TTC/ARIES flux trapping workshop 2018, CERN.

This behaviour triggered an emergency program for LCLS-II, where single cell cavities were built from different Nb sheets and then different high-temperature treatments were tried to study if the poor flux expulsion of some Nb types could be improved. This was partly successful but some batches still could not reach the required flux expulsion, even with 900° C heat treatments.

At CERN the production of the 400 MHz HL-LHC Crab Cavities is starting and we are looking for a way to characterise the flux expulsion of Nb sheet material without the need to make cavities out of each different material sample. While the target specs for the crab cavities ($Q = 5.4 \times 10^{10}$ at 3.4 MV deflecting voltage) seem not very demanding for a 400 MHz cavity, they can become a challenge due to the extensive cold forming of the Nb sheets, which in turn requires an unusually high yield strength of $Rp_{0.2\%} > 65$ MPa for this type of cavities. High yield strength and heavy cold-work usually implies decreased flux expulsion, so we want to understand the possible degradation for this particular cavity type and we want to measure the flux expulsion of sheet material, which fulfils the requirements for high yield strength. Furthermore, CERN has five 5-cell 704 MHz cavities, which so far show a slightly higher residual resistance than comparable 800 MHz cavities. Here we want to investigate on samples if the flux expulsion can be improved with heat treatments above 650°C.

3.2 THE FLUX LENS

A stand-alone instrument to measure flux expulsion efficiency should have the following characteristics:

- Use of small flat samples, easy to cut from sheet material.
- The B -field enhancement measured when going to the Meissner state should be comparable to observations on cavities. The expulsion ratio should reach: $B_{sc}/B_{nc} > 1.7$.
- Precise control of the temperature gradient across the sample. This should enable a good reproducibility of the results and will allow to measure flux expulsion as a function of the temperature gradient.
- Use of a cryocooler is desirable as it makes the measurement independent from cryogenic installations.
- Low sensitivity to B -field direction. In this case measuring the expulsion of Earth's magnetic field should be sufficient. This also implies that no additional magnets are needed.

The basic idea to fulfil these specifications was to use round samples with a hole in the middle. When cooling from the outside (Fig. 8), the disc undergoes the superconducting transition such that the expelled flux is pushed towards the central hole (Fig. 9).

Figure 8: Cooling down of the flux lens.

The better the tested material expels the flux, the more the field is enhanced in the center where it can be conveniently measured by a standard Bartington flux-gate.

Figure 9: Flux expulsion in a superconducting disc.

After a first successful proof-of-principle test a prototype instrument was built, which is compatible with a cryocooler available at CERN. The outer diameter of the disc is cooled by conduction while the centre of the disc can be heated by a resistor. This configuration allows precise adjustment of the temperature gradient across the sample as the material undergoes the transition to the superconducting state. Results from the first measurement campaign showed a maximum measured field enhancement factor of 1.83 for a 3 mm thick high-RRR unworked Nb disc (theoretical maximum value: 2.08). The results in Fig. 10 show how the heater is used to push the disc centre above T_c and how it can also be used to reduce the temperature gradient, which then results in a lower magnetic flux measured by the probe. The device was presented in February 2020 at [10] and a refereed paper is in preparation.

Figure 10: First flux expulsion measurement with the CERN flux lens

4. Conclusions & future plans

Within the frame of the ARIES WP4, CERN developed a passive and active magnetic shielding configuration for a 4-cavity cryomodule that is able to suppress ambient fields to the sub-micro-Tesla level. The magnetic shielding of the empty cryomodule vessel was then measured and it was confirmed that it is not necessary to use non-magnetic steel for this kind of application and that the existing low level of magnetisation, which is mainly due to the welds, does not need a demagnetization campaign. Both facts contribute to a considerable cost saving for future modules of this kind.

Within the frame of the ARIES WP4 collaboration CERN also developed and tested a new instrument, called “flux lens” for quick and reproducible measurements of the flux expulsion efficiency of Niobium sheet material. The instrument will be used for material characterisation for the HL-LHC crab cavities and furthermore for R&D to establish a relation between cold-working and different heat treatments of Niobium and the resulting flux expulsion efficiency. With the flux lens it is no longer necessary to build test cavities out of different sheet material in order to assess its flux expulsion efficiency. This results in a much faster way to assess Nb sheet material and it brings substantial cost savings. Furthermore, it simplifies systematic studies of flux expulsion as a function of different material treatment techniques, with the goal of lowering the surface resistance of superconducting cavities and thus lowering the power consumption of future accelerators. The method has caught the interest of the international community and JLAB is keen to collaborate with CERN to use the flux lens for the series testing of Nb sheet material for the LCLS-II cavities.

5. References

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
BCS	Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer
LCLS-II	Linac Coherent Light Source 2
HL-LHC	High-Luminosity LHC
JLAB	Jefferson Laboratory